

Developing A Simplified Maintenance & Rehabilitation Activity Prioritization Tool for Afghanistan Roads

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Abstract: Roads are one of the most important factor of life, and maintenance & rehabilitation of them are very vital and challenging for a country. Afghanistan is one of those countries which face the challenges of low-budget, computerized office works and skilled personnel. Regarding to budget limitation pavement maintenance and rehabilitation activity prioritization is obligatory. Currently, a technology based, and simplified maintenance activity prioritization tool are an essential need of the country. The aim of this research is to develop a tool which prioritize the maintenance and rehabilitation activities by considering some factors such as pavement condition index, road width, traffic volume, residential importance as well as maintenance and rehabilitation cost. Since characterizing a model that presents each one of those variables was difficult, a simplified model named TOPSIS was denoted for the issue of prioritization. TOPSIS model lets you have a more precise ranking for the outcome. Considering the problem, Visual Basic have the ability to easily code any type of model and present a graphical display of the model. A source code was developed and Visual Basic was used for computations coding, graphical display of results and generating reports. The developed model indicates that more than two criteria/weights are very important for prioritizing the alternatives/activities. The developed tool can prioritize the maintenance and rehabilitation activities and generate different database for further use in ArcGIS.

Keywords: Road Maintenance and Rehabilitation; Activity Prioritization; TOPSIS; Vb.Net

I. INTRODUCTION

Afghanistan is lacking proper road maintenance which resulted in a huge amount of investment loss in the past 10 years. The emphasis of the government and donors was on development of new roads regardless of understanding and focusing the maintenance capacity and budget. It is therefore over 4 billion USD investment in road assets is in the threat of loss. Recently the government and donors have recognized the issue and have focused to strengthen the capacity in the maintenance sector. One of the main issues in the maintenance sector is that there is no technology and data based decision support tool for engineers to properly plan maintenance of roads and prepare long term strategic plans for maintenance.

Currently road maintenance prioritization is on ad-hoc basis without proper need assessment and technical evaluation. It is therefore an indispensable need for the government to have a technology based decision support tool to give planners and decision makers'

objective based understanding for decisions in the maintenance programs development.

Since the rate of road traffic growth expands considerably speedier than the expansion in the length of paved roads, it prompts a generous increment of wear and harming impacts of cars on to the road bringing about an expanded interest for repair and restoration. Undesirably this pattern will raise in the close term [1].

Economy and the country's road administration effectively hunts for new types of management, including new ways to deal with orchestrating road maintenance administrations. If there should be an occurrence of an effective usage of this research, the road maintenance division of Afghanistan will completely change to the quality-based road maintenance strategy.

The aim of this research is to develop a tool which prioritize the maintenance and rehabilitation activities by considering some factors such as pavement condition index PCI, road width, traffic volume,

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residential importance as well as maintenance and rehabilitation cost. Since characterizing a model that presents each one of those variables was difficult, a simplified model named TOPSIS was denoted for the issue of prioritization. TOPSIS model lets you have a more precise ranking for the outcome.

Considering the problem, Visual Basic have the ability to easily code any type of model and present a graphical display of the model. A source code was developed and Visual Basic was used for computations, graphical display of results and generating reports.

The advantages of this model are to carry out the prioritization process computations automatically and give as an optimized ranking table as well as generate different type of database for using in ArcGIS for further displaying, analyzing and preparing well planned pavement maintenance and rehabilitation activities.

II. TOPSIS MODEL

The Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is a multicriteria decision analysis method, which was originally developed by Hwang and Yoon in 1981 [2] with further developments by Yoon in 1987 [3], and Hwang, Lai and Liu in 1993 [4].

TOPSIS is based on the concept that the chosen alternative should have the shortest geometric distance from the positive ideal solution (PIS) and the longest geometric distance from the negative ideal solution (NIS) [5].

It is a method of compensatory aggregation that compares a set of alternatives by identifying weights for each criterion, normalizing scores for each criterion and calculating the geometric distance between each alternative and the ideal alternative, which is the best score in each criterion. An assumption of TOPSIS is that the criteria are monotonically increasing or decreasing. Normalization is usually required as the parameters or criteria are often of incongruous dimensions in multicriteria problems [6][7].

Compensatory methods such as TOPSIS allow tradeoffs between criteria, where a poor result in one criterion can be negated by a good result in another criterion. This provides a more realistic form of modelling than non-compensatory methods, which include or exclude alternative solutions based on hard cutoffs [8].

A. The Algorithm

The TOPSIS method evaluates the following decision matrix which contains m alternatives associated with n attributes (or criteria):

$$D = \begin{matrix} & X_1 & X_2 & \dots & X_j & \dots & X_n \\ A_1 & x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1j} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ A_2 & x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2j} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ A_i & x_{i1} & x_{i2} & \dots & x_{ij} & \dots & x_{in} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ A_m & x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mj} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

Where

A_i = the i th alternative considered,

x_{ij} = the numerical outcome of the i th alternative with respect to the j th criterion.

TOPSIS assumes that each attribute in the decision matrix takes either monotonically increasing or monotonically decreasing utility. Since all criteria cannot be assumed to be of equal importance, the method receives a set of weights from the decision maker. For the sake of simplicity, the proposed method will be presented as a series of successive steps.

Step 1. Construct the normalized decision matrix: This process tries to transform the various attribute dimensions into non-dimensional attributes, which allows comparison across the attributes. An element r_{ij} of the normalized decision matrix R can be calculated as:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m X_{ij}^2} \quad (2)$$

Where

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Step 2. Construct the weighted normalized decision matrix: A set of weights $W = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_j, \dots, w_n)$, $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, from the decision maker is accommodated to the decision matrix in this step. This matrix can be calculated by multiplying each column of the matrix R with its associated weight w the weighted normalized decision matrix V is equal to:

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 r_{11} & w_2 r_{12} & \dots & w_j r_{1j} & \dots & w_n r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ w_1 r_{i1} & w_2 r_{i2} & \dots & w_j r_{ij} & \dots & w_n r_{in} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & & \vdots \\ w_1 r_{m1} & w_2 r_{m2} & \dots & w_j r_{mj} & \dots & w_n r_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Step 3. Determine ideal and negative- ideal solutions: Let the two artificial alternatives A^+ and A^- be defined as:

$$A^+ = \left\{ \left(\max_i V_{ij} \right), i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$A^- = \left\{ \left(\min_i V_{ij} \right), i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\} \quad (5)$$

Then it is certain that the two created alternatives A^+ and A^- indicate the most preferable alternative (ideal solution) and the least preferable alternative (negative-ideal solution) respectively.

Step 4. Calculate the separation measure: The separation between each alternative can be measured by the n -dimensional Euclidean distance. The separation of each alternative from the ideal one is then given by:

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - V_j^+)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the separation from the negative-ideal solution is given by:

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - V_j^-)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (7)$$

Step 5. Calculate the relative closeness to the ideal solution: the relative closeness of A_i with respect to A^+ is defined as:

$$C_{i+} = \frac{S_i^-}{(S_i^+ + S_i^-)} \quad (8)$$

Where

$$0 < C_{i+} < 1, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

It is clear that, $C_{i+} = 1$ if $A_i = A^+$ and $C_{i+} = 0$ if $A_i = A^-$. An alternative A_i is closer to A^+ as C_{i+} approaches to 1.

Step 6. Rank the preference order: A set of alternatives can now be preference ranked according to the descending order of C_{i+} .

III. CURRENT SITUATION

In developed countries, the Road Maintenance Management System contains five main systems such as Pavement Management System (PMS), Bridge Management System, Non-pavement Management System, Database Management System, and Maintenance Follow-up Management System. Specially the management of road maintenance activity functions as one of the components of the road maintenance management system are consists of the strategic planning, programming, preparation and operation [9].

Normally, in Afghanistan the Road Maintenance activities undergoes in a process of two main scheme: Emergency Road Maintenance and Seasonal Road Maintenance [1]. The emergency road maintenance activities on road surface which happens unexpectedly due to the floods, traffic loads, earthquake, ... etc. Which the seasonal road maintenance activities take place as bellows:

In the spring after passing the winter the cleaning of side drainages from mud, stones and other things which blocks them. Surveying the culverts and maintaining them in case if blocked. Maintenance of road surface damages which occurred due to rain and snow followings and installation of damaged traffic sings.

In the summer, mainly the road maintenance activities, graveling and surfacing activities take place in this phase.

In the fall season, beside the checking of drainages, culverts and cutting the grass, the preparation for winter by installing the snow blocking nets and storing the sand & salt will take place.

In the winter season, mainly the road maintenance activities are snow cleaning which will always be open to the public. Using of sand and salt on snow and ice for melting them. Also, constructing the structures for preventing avalanches (if needed).

Generally, in most developed countries, the common tools/software which is used for undertaking the road maintenance activities computations are Micro Paver and HDM 4. Currently, using this software are almost

impossible in Afghanistan in terms of financing, data requirements and complexity.

Currently, in Afghanistan specially in road maintenance sector the decision makers don't use any tools/software for computations. Usually, they do the computations manually, which is very time consuming [1].

The new tool which developed in this study are suitable in Afghanistan to simplify the road maintenance activities calculation with low cost and very simple data.

IV. TOOL DEVELOPMENT

With the growth of the alternatives and attributes the measurement of the problem is increasing respectively. Which need various mathematical operations in order to have an ideal answer. Accordingly, the assistance of a tool may be very valuable to automatically carry out all the projected model calculations. The Tool was developed using Visual Studio 2015 and named Maintenance and Rehabilitation Activity Prioritization MRAP Tool, Fig. 1, shows the main page and tool name. The operation process is according to the steps which clarified in section II. In the following, the explanation of the developed tool will carry out through using sample data. Fig. 2, shows the flowchart of calculation steps.

The problems of road maintenance activities selection will be identified by the decision makers. The sample Data Types which we used in this sample process are the alternatives (roads) and attributes (such as PCI, road width, traffic volume, maintenance budget, and political, social & environmental importance factor of the respective roads). Fig. 3, shows the computation page which user should select the New button for starting a new project. Fig. 4, shows the criteria selection page, the user should enter the dimension of alternatives with their respective attributes for creating the decision matrix.

Fig. 1 Developed tool name

Fig. 2 Calculation steps flowchart

Fig. 3 Computation main page

Fig. 4 Criteria selection

Next, the user should fill the decision matrix with the required data. The user should insert the data in the columns roads section name of Road Name, PCI on W1, road width on W2 (m), Traffic Volume on W3, Maintenance Budget on W4 (\$), and Political, Social & Environmental Importance factor on W5 (1-9) columns respectively. Once the decision matrix filled by the important values the user should enter the respective weights for each criterion manually in the Weights Table section. Fig. 5, shows the snapshot of data entry table. Fig. 6, shows the snapshot of the weights table. The attributes and weights information should be all in numeric.

	Road Name	W 1	W 2	W 3	W 4	W 5
1	Road 1	75	8	3200	1200	7
2	Road 2	75	8	3200	1200	7
3	Road 3	85	8	3500	1400	6
4	Road 4	85	8	3500	1400	6
5	Road 5	80	8	3100	1300	5
6	Road 6	80	8	3100	1300	5
7	Road 7	82	8	3400	1100	8
8	Road 8	82	8	3400	1100	8
9	Road 9	88	6	2700	600	4
10	Road 10	88	6	2700	600	4
11	Road 11	74	6	2600	700	3
12	Road 12	74	6	2600	700	3
13	Road 13	78	6	2900	650	3
14	Road 14	78	6	2900	650	3
15	Road 15	90	6	2850	750	2
16	Road 16	90	6	2850	750	2
17	Road 17	92	6	2750	500	2

Fig. 5 Data entry table

ID	Road Name	Similarities	Ranking
7	Road 7	0.799	1
8	Road 8	0.799	1
1	Road 1	0.7766	2
2	Road 2	0.7766	2
3	Road 3	0.7729	3
4	Road 4	0.7729	3
5	Road 5	0.6359	4
6	Road 6	0.6359	4
9	Road 9	0.2829	5
10	Road 10	0.2829	5
19	Road 19	0.2475	6
20	Road 20	0.2475	6
15	Road 15	0.2269	7
16	Road 16	0.2269	7
13	Road 13	0.1939	8
14	Road 14	0.1939	8
11	Road 11	0.1907	9

Fig. 9 Optimized ranking table

	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5
	0.22	0.12	0.26	0.24	0.20

Fig. 6 Weight table

Fig. 7 Run the project

Fig. 8 Ranking order

After filling the data entry table and weights table the user should hit the Run button to run the project and carry out all the required TOPSIS model computations automatically by the equations (1) ~ (8) and give us the closest ideal solution, Fig. 7.

Next, if the process run without any failure the user should select the Ranking button to automatically rank the alternatives in ascending order and give us an optimized ranking table, Fig. 8. Fig. 8, shows the snapshot of the optimized ranking order table.

Finally, after completing all the process and ranking the alternatives the user can export the data into Excel and Text File formats for using in ArcGIS for generating various type of thematic maps in order to give the decision makers to select a better maintenance strategic plans, Fig. 10. Fig.11, shows the snapshot of the sample exported data into text file format.

The values in the similarities column of Fig. 11, shows the closeness to the best options and Roads 7 & 8 ranked as 1 due to the highest traffic volume both 3200 and highest environmental importance factor both 7, which indicates that these two road have more users on daily basis and are very important for local people.

Fig. 10 Exporting data

ID	Road Name	Similarities	Ranking
7	Road 7	0.799	1
8	Road 8	0.799	1
1	Road 1	0.7766	2
2	Road 2	0.7766	2
3	Road 3	0.7729	3
4	Road 4	0.7729	3
5	Road 5	0.6359	4
6	Road 6	0.6359	4
9	Road 9	0.2829	5
10	Road 10	0.2829	5
19	Road 19	0.2475	6
20	Road 20	0.2475	6
15	Road 15	0.2269	7
16	Road 16	0.2269	7
13	Road 13	0.1939	8
14	Road 14	0.1939	8
11	Road 11	0.1907	9
12	Road 12	0.1907	9
17	Road 17	0.1652	10
18	Road 18	0.1652	10

Fig. 11 Exported text file format

V. CONCLUSSION

In this study, the Tool were developed in Visual Studio in order to simplify the computation process. With the growth of alternatives and criteria the computation process increases respectively. So the TOPSIS model considered for dealing this long computations to give us mathematically ideal and optimized answer.

The main objective of the developed tool is to prioritize the maintenance and rehabilitation activity. For using this tool there should be at least 2+ alternatives with minimum 2+ criteria/weights. This tool will allow the decision makers to accelerate the computation process and select suitable projects which give freedom and time for spending more time in

preparing the current and future strategic plans in road maintenance sector. The developed tool allows the user to transfer the data into database in order to use in ArcGIS for preparing different thematic maps and budget scenarios maps.

In the future works, I will confirm that this tool is useful by comparing it with other similar tools in terms of advantages and disadvantages, pricing, and requirements of responsible organization for maintenance and rehabilitation activities.

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